

THE WAYS OF GIVING APPROPRIATE INSTRUCTIONS

Auelbekova Balxadisha Serik qizi

E-mail: serikqizibalxadisha@gmail.com

Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

English language and literature faculty student

Scientific advisor: Burkhanova Mamura Gulyamovna

mamuraburxanova@gmail.com

Abstract: The significance of providing clear directions in the second-language classroom will be explored in this article along with the justification for doing so methods for communicating instructions clearly.

Keywords: Giving instruction, directions, misunderstandings, task's objectives, over-instruction.

Introduction. Giving instructions is a phrase we use to ask or instruct someone else to do something. Instruction (sometimes termed imperatives) (also called imperatives). The individual getting instructions must either follow them or cease doing what they are currently doing. The individual who must follow the instructions receives them immediately. Therefore, guidelines are one of the few English sentence structures that does not require a subject! generally "you" is the topic (understood). Who should perform the action if there is any question The "naming" vocative form is used while giving instructions.

The majority of us can remember an instance where the facilitator gave directions but we weren't sure exactly what we were supposed to accomplish. Additionally, the majority of us have had professional experiences instructing students in ways that they didn't understand or found confusing. Although occasionally making mistakes when providing instructions is understandable, developing this skill is a crucial component of effective classroom teaching.⁷⁹

According to Scrivener (2011) and Ur (1996), instructions and how they are delivered can make or break a class. Research shows, in the words of Ur (1996, 16), that "students view the capacity to explain things clearly as one of the most significant traits of a competent teacher."

⁷⁹ Asher, J. J. 2009. Learning another language through actions. 7th ed. Los Gatos, CA: Sky Oaks Productions.

For instance, Wragg and Wood's (1984, 82) research discovered that "the ability to explain is most highly regarded" in a teacher.

Methods of analysis. Often, with clearer directions, shrugs and misunderstanding may be avoided. Giving students precise directions may have a significant impact on their achievement in the classroom, which might occasionally surprise teachers. When provided clear instructions, pupils are better able to interact with the subject matter and eventually have more beneficial experiences. There are a number of measures teachers may take to make sure that their pupils comprehend instructions and can finish tasks without difficulty.

1. Speak in precise language

The gold standard for providing clear instructions was written by Chilcoat and Stahl (<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00098655.1986.9959298?journalCode=vtch20>) thirty-three years ago. To help pupils grasp what is expected of them, they suggested utilizing succinct, comprehensive sentences and exact, concrete language. Additionally, they advised staying away from ambiguous words like "some," "a few," and "a couple" and use nouns rather than pronouns—especially when instructing younger pupils.

A "how to" for aspiring instructors. (<https://www.wgu.edu/blog/2017/12/how-become-teacher.html>)

The expectations of the job or assignment should also be stated by the teacher in unambiguous terms. Students can better comprehend and comply with your instructions if you specify what they must do, how they must accomplish it, and by when. Both the teacher's and the student's jobs may be made clearer and simpler by including a solid, comprehensive rubric with the assignment.

2. Recite your instructions again

We often take it for granted that our students will pay attention while we talk, but anybody who has taught for longer than five minutes is aware that this isn't always the case. A teacher may provide instructions only to discover that their students haven't been paying attention or have just partially understood them. To make sure that every kid is paying attention and knows what has to be done, take a quick look around the room, refocus the conversation, and utilize repetition. I frequently write assignment instructions on our computer platform, on the assignment sheet, and on the board so that students may refer to them while they work. (<https://www.wgu.edu/online-teaching-degrees.html?refer id=115046&ch=RTCLS>)⁸⁰

⁸⁰<https://www.wgu.edu/online-teaching-degrees.html?refer id=115046&ch=RTCLS>)

3. Describe the Task's Objective.

Students are better able to enjoy the experience when you explain to them why they are being requested to do an assignment. Students will feel more comfortable taking on the assignment if the activity is related to their prior knowledge, courses, or subject presented.

4. Ensure that your students comprehend

Ask your pupils to repeat or restate the instructions you just gave them. Ask them detailed questions on the specifications. Describe any areas that are unclear. Give students comments that will aid in their comprehension and completion of the assignment.

Results and analysis. If your directions are clear and reasonable, your youngster is more likely to comply. The following advice can help you teach your child.

Don't try to over-instruct your youngster. Keep instructions for things that actually matter to you, including safety concerns. For instance, when you cross the road, your youngster has to grasp your hand. Instead of giving your youngster directions, attempt to make collaboration enjoyable by making dull tasks into challenges. How many toys can you put away before the timer goes off?

Here are some pointers for when you do need to train your child:

Obtain your child's attention by approaching them at eye level and giving them a gentle touch.⁸¹

Literature analysis. There are differing views on whether imparting knowledge in a second language (L2) classroom while using one's first language (L1). Instruction-giving is a situation that justifies the use of the L1 in the L2 classroom, according to Atkinson (1987), Auerbach (1993), and Macaro (1997). Cook (2016) and Ur (1996) concur that using the mother tongue may be necessary in some situations. According to Salaberri (1995) and Gardner and Gardner (2000), students should be exposed to English usage from the very first lesson. This would help them comprehend that foreign languages are not only things to be studied but also, and more crucially, a means of communication.⁸² As a result, from the start of a course, teachers should work to incorporate the L2 required for instruction-giving. It goes without saying that the instructor must consent before using the pupils' native tongue. Understands it to some extent. the multilingual classes, it is a delusion to anticipate the Multiple explanations will be managed by the teacher languages. If professors who do this are unable to

⁸¹ Burkhanova M.G. (2021). SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL LOOK OF A CULTURAL MAN. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 12 (104), 422-425. <https://dx.doi.org/10.15863/TAS.2021.02.94.6> Doi:

⁸² Brown, S., and J. Larson-Hall. 2012. Second language acquisition myths: Applying second language research to classroom teaching. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press

communicate in the language of their students (s) understand how to communicate their directions Teachers who teach in English have the option to talk in the first language of their kids to make themselves additionally recognized in English.

Conclusion. Although providing effective instruction is a talent that can be mastered, it is also a crucial component of a session that is successful. That is frequently missed during teacher preparation and in classrooms, programs the contrary often great lesson fails due of The delivery of instructions was flawed. Making the assumption that giving good Learning how to follow directions comes easy. Both Teachers who are in-service and in preservice must be watchful of appropriate methods of education as well as their unique techniques for doing so, delivery, as well as suggestions for improvement.

REFERENCES

1. (<https://www.wgu.edu/blog/2017/12/how-become-teacher.html>)
2. <https://www.wgu.edu/online-teaching-degrees.html?referid=115046&ch=RTCLS>)
3. Asher, J. J. 2009. Learning another language through actions. 7th ed. Los Gatos, CA: Sky Oaks Productions.
4. Atkinson, D. 1987. The mother tongue in the classroom: A neglected resource? *ELT Journal* 41 (4): 241–247.
5. Auerbach, E. R. 1993. Reexamining English Only in the ESL classroom. *TESOL Quarterly* 27 (1): 9–32.
6. Brown, S., and J. Larson-Hall. 2012. Second language acquisition myths: Applying second language research to classroom teaching. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press.
7. Burkhanova M.G. (2021). SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL LOOK OF A CULTURAL MAN. *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science*, 12 (104), 422-425. <https://dx.doi.org/10.15863/TAS.2021.02.94.6> Doi:
8. Burkhanova M.G. (2022). AXIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF STUDENT MORALITY. *European journal of research development and sustainability*. Vol 3 N 2. <https://www.scholarzest.com/>